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Review Paper

Synergistic Efficacy and Mechanistic Pathways of Curcumin-Based Combinations in the Management of Inflammation: A Comprehensive Review

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ABSTRACT

As inflammation plays a significant part in the pathophysiology of many diseases, it has emerged as a therapeutic target for the creation of novel pharmaceutical treatments. Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory medications and the steroid class of medications are known to have certain adverse effects when used to treat inflammation. Therefore, reducing inflammation is essential to reducing the disease's severity. Combining more than one drug to prevent inflammation in a synergistic way is one way to solve this issue. Over the past few decades, a lot of study has been done on the anti-inflammatory properties of curcumin, a bioactive component, particularly in the Zingiberaceae family, which offers a number of health benefits. Combinations of curcumin have been observed to improve anti-inflammatory properties. A review of the literature on curcumin combination studies has been conducted using several electronic sources, such as PubMed and Google Scholar. In this review, we provide an overview of curcumin's pharmacological action when combined with additional substances, with a focus on the synergistic anti-inflammatory effects. We offer enhanced bioavailability, which boosts antioxidants' ability to block inflammatory mediators, receptors, and important signaling pathways, in order to figure out how combinations produce a synergistic effect. This review offers information and promotes further investigation into the combination of pharmaceuticals to reduce inflammation.

INTRODUCTION

There are around 200 various types of inflammatory diseases. Inflammation is indicated by the names of diseases that end in "itis."

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Although inflammation from chronic illnesses like cholangitis can induce colon cancer, acute inflammation is thought of as a defensive mechanism since it promotes recovery. Since inflammation contributes to the development of many chronic illnesses, including autoimmune, endocrine, neurological, and cardiovascular disorders, it will worsen these conditions if left untreated (1). Numerous enzymes, cytokines, chemokines, and polypeptide hormones that might mediate inflammation have been identified as a result of research into the molecular mechanisms behind inflammation. TNF, IL-1 α , interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β), IL-6, interleukin-8 (IL-8), IL-18, chemokine, matrix metalloproteinase 9 (MMP-9), vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2), and 5-lipoxygenase (5-LOX) are among them. If the numbers of monocytes, neutrophils, eosinophils, and mast cells are not managed, additional immune cells will be drawn in to produce more proinflammatory chemicals. Because the process creates nitric oxide (NO) and reactive oxygen species (ROS), which harm the structure, function, and integrity of lipids, proteins, and nucleic acids, the result will be a variety of chronic disorders(2)The transcription factor of nucleus- $\kappa\beta$ (NF- $\kappa\beta$) significantly controls the expression of this gene (3). Because it causes the release of several kinds of cytokines, chemokines, adhesion molecules, and leukocyte recruitment, the NF- $\kappa\beta$ pathway weakens the NF- $\kappa\beta$ pathway as a therapeutic approach for chronic inflammation(4). Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, for example, can raise the risk of adverse gastrointestinal, renal, and cardiovascular effects. Anti-inflammatory drugs temporarily reduce inflammation symptoms, but the disease progresses over time(5). Although anti-inflammatory corticosteroid medications have a potent therapeutic benefit for a number of conditions, prolonged use also has negative side effects(6).

Many rhizomes of the *Curcuma longa* and Zingiberaceae family contain curcumin, a secondary metabolite used as a medicinal plant with anti-inflammatory and antioxidant qualities (7). Up until today, curcumin has been used widely in traditional medicine. Numerous studies have been conducted to understand the medicinal uses of curcumin, 1, 7-bis (4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)-1,6-heptadien-3,5-dione, and the yellow pigment in turmeric rhizome, particularly in the Asian region(8). Because curcumin interacts with numerous inflammatory routes and processes, it has pharmacological effects on decreasing inflammation. Curcumin has been shown to have a number of health advantages, including anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, chemopreventive, and chemotherapeutic properties(9). Human clinical trials, animal models, and cultured cells have all shown the pharmacological action(10). Opportunities for treating drug resistance and toxicity are presented by compound combination studies(11). Severe and chronic illnesses are treated with a combination of medications. Achieving a synergistic therapeutic impact, lowering the dosage to minimize toxicity, and limiting or postponing the establishment of drug resistance are just a few of the many therapy benefits that this combination offers(12). The purpose of this review is to examine how curcumin can work in concert with two or more other medications to have an anti-inflammatory effect as opposed to just one application. The anti-inflammatory benefits that emerge from combining different components with curcumin are summarized in this paper, with a focus on the outcomes of the synergistic anti-inflammatory impact. The advantages of this review include scientific data about the combined effects of curcumin with other ingredients to reduce inflammation. It is anticipated that the review's findings would bring clarity on methods for managing inflammation that work in concert with

one another to deliver a successful treatment with minimal side effects.

METHOD

To identify all papers on the topic up until March 2026, a thorough search of the PubMed and Google Scholar databases was carried out. The keywords "curcumin, combination, and anti-inflammatory" were used to locate relevant papers. Articles utilizing a combination of curcumin components (drugs or phytochemicals) that can have anti-inflammatory effects, comparing the effects of curcumin alone with a combination, and producing anti-inflammatory effects that are synergistic or superior to using curcumin alone were all included in this review. A few English-language publications were chosen on the basis that they offer comparison information between curcumin's single usage and its combination. Conference, review, and thesis articles were not considered primary articles. found 67 main articles of components combined with curcumin (Table 1). These chosen articles were based on research on curcumin and its combination conducted both in vitro and in vivo. During the selection of these articles, we reviewed them primarily by evaluating the kinds of test animals, cells, induction agent employed, and the results of these combinations.

Determination of the effects of a combination

In medicine, it is common practice to combine several kinds of drug components. Combinations of two or more elements can provide additive, synergistic, or antagonistic effects; a single method does not necessarily improve its particular pharmacological impact. Worldwide, the Chou-Talalay approach has been utilized in conjunction with drug research and effect assessments. According to(13), the combination index (CI) shows additive impact when $CI = 1$, synergism when $CI < 1$, and antagonism when $CI > 1$. Our

investigation revealed that this approach is frequently employed for medication combination research. The following formula was used to calculate the combination of indexes.:

$$CI = \frac{(D)_1}{(D_m)_1} + \frac{(D)_2}{(D_m)_2}$$

(D)1 and (D)2 are the concentrations of components X and Y which are combined to produce a value of IC50. (Dm)1 and (Dm)2 are the concentrations of components X and Y given singly and obtained the value of IC50. The same method used in CI was used to determine the cumulative effect in test animals. Combination studies, however, show that medications have limitations, including higher costs, longer processing times, and population and group restrictions. In this review, we were able to quantify the combined in vitro effect by comparing the drug's combined and uncombined effects. A straightforward formula of $X + Y > X$ or $X + Y > Y$ produced the effect. It can be determined that a medication combination has a synergistic impact in clinical trial research if it produces a better pharmacological effect than monotherapy(12). It is known from this review that a number of in vitro investigations have employed the CI method. Only the curcumin combination with a synergistic anti-inflammatory effect was explored in studies that used test animals to determine the synergy effect based on a comparison between combination and single use.

Effect of curcumin on anti-inflammation

Several pharmacological effects of curcumin, particularly its anti-inflammatory qualities, have been documented. It is well known that curcumin can reduce both acute and chronic inflammation(8). Curcumin can act alone or in combination through a number of different methods. Curcumin inhibits the COX and LOX

pathways, arachidonic acid metabolic activities, and prostaglandin formation as part of its anti-inflammatory mechanism. COX-2 expression is selectively inhibited by curcumin(14, 15). Compared to the COX-1 enzyme, curcumin is more active against the COX-2 enzyme(16). By decreasing COX-2 and preventing prostaglandin E2 synthesis (PGE2), curcumin can stop anti-inflammatory reactions in synovial fibroblasts(17). Cyclooxygenase activity on human platelets and 5-LOX inhibition on rat peritoneal neutrophils both demonstrate curcumin's anti-inflammatory properties(18). Because curcumin can lower the production of proinflammatory cytokines like IL-8, inflammatory protein monocyte-1, chemotactic protein monocyte-1 (MCP-1), IL-1 β , and tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α), its ability to suppress inflammation has been demonstrated in both in vitro and in vivo studies(19, 20). Curcumin inhibits the effects of high hyperglycemia and the release of TNF- α , MCP-1, IL-6, and IL-8 in cultured monocytes(21). Curcumin has demonstrated its effectiveness as a potent asthma reliever in another trial. This action is caused by a mechanism that lowers immunoglobulin E2 and inhibits the production of IL-2, IL-4, and IL-5(22). By controlling the production of NF- κ β , activator protein 1, inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS), TNF- α , and IL-6, curcumin also exhibits anti-inflammatory effects in pancreatitis rats(23). The

in vitro test demonstrated curcumin's capacity to inhibit the NF- κ β and mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) pathways; it also reduces TNF- α and IL-6 in BV2 microglia cells challenged with lipopolysaccharide(24).

By lowering ROS production and boosting enzymatic activity, such as the expression of methionine sulfoxide reductase A, curcumin activity might lessen inflammation. Additionally, it raises enzymes including glutathione peroxidase (GPx), catalase (CAT), and superoxide dismutase (SOD)(25). Curcumin at a dose of 200 mg/kg can help boost SOD activity, CAT, and total liver antioxidant capacity in rats given thallium acetate(26). Because of its antioxidant properties, curcumin can function as an oxidative DNA cleaver and a NO scavenger(27). Curcumin also inhibits the expression of the iNOS gene in BALB/c mice recovered from peritoneal macrophages and livers of mice treated with lipopolysaccharide (LPS)(28). In RAW 264.7 cells treated with lipopolysaccharide or interferon- γ , curcumin can reduce NO generation, iNOS, and messenger ribonucleic acid (mRNA) protein expression(29). Lipid peroxidation, a process seen in rat liver microsomes, has been demonstrated to be inhibited by curcumin(30). Curcuminoids also exhibit antioxidant action in rat brain homogenates(31).

Table 1. Curcumin's synergistic anti-inflammatory effects

No.	Component	Pharmacology model	Induction/treatment	Result	Reference
1	Piperine	Male Swiss albino mice	LPS	Suppresses proinflammatory cytokines (IL-1 β and TNF- α)	(32)

2	Piperine	Male Wistar mouse	Olfactory bulbectomy model	Lower brain TNF- α and caspase 3 levels	(33)
3	Piperine	Male C57BL/6J mice	High fat	Downregulate s proinflammatory cytokines (IL-6 and TNF α)	(34)
4	Piperine	Epithelial cells HT-29	TNF- α	Inhibits TNF- α and COX-2	(35)
5	Piperine	Albino Wistar Rat	-	Increases bioavailability	(36)
6	Piperine	Male C57BL/6 mice	High fat	Suppresses proinflammatory cytokines IL-1 β	(37)
7	Piperine	Male Wistar rats	Haloperidol	Inhibits NO, TNF- α , and NF- κ β	(38)
8	Piperine	RAW 264.7	RANKL	Inhibit osteoclastogenesis	(39)
9	Resveratrol	Male Wistar rats	Fipronil	Increases GSH, GPx, SOD, and CAT; MDA and NO decrease	(40)
10	Resveratrol	Chondrocyte	IL-1 β	Inhibits expression IL-1 β , COX-2, MMP-3, MMP-9, and VEGF	(41)
11	Resveratrol	Colon cancer HCT-116	-	Reduces proliferation and stimulates apoptosis with attenuation of NF- κ β activity	(42)

12	Resveratrol	HO radical	-	Resveratrol protects curcumin from degradation	(43)
13	Resveratrol	Male Wistar rat	Complete Freund's adjuvant (CFA)	Reduces paw thickness and arthritis score	(44)
14	Resveratrol	Male Laka mice	Benzo[a]pyrene	Brings down COX-2 activity; improves p21 protein expression	(45)
15	Resveratrol	EA.hy 926 human endothelial cells; C57BL/6 mouse aorta	TNF- α -induced vascular inflammation	Curcumin (5 μ M) + resveratrol (5 μ M) synergistically reduced monocyte adhesion, VCAM-1, and MCP-1; combination strongly inhibited NF- κ B p65 nuclear translocation; combination index \sim 0.78.	(46)
16	Resveratrol	Weaned piglets	-	Inhibits IL-1 β and TNF- α	(47)
17	Resveratrol	Male Wistar rats	Cotton ligature	Inhibits IL-1 β and IL-4	(48)
18	Resveratrol	Male adult Wistar	Aluminum chloride	Inhibits COX-2 and increases SOD, GSH, CAT, and glutathione S-transferase	(49)
19	Resveratrol-curcumin hybrid	AOM/DSS-induced colon	Colon pre-neoplastic lesions	Synthetic resveratrol-curcumin	(50)

		carcinogenesis mice		hybrid reduced ACF, β -catenin, COX-2, NF- κ B more than parent compounds; inhibited Wnt/ β -catenin signaling	
20	Quercetin	Male albino rats	Carrageenan	Increases GSH and HO-1 mRNA; reduces paw thickness, MDA, NO, and TNF- α	(51)
21	Quercetin	Albino rat	Diazinon	Increases antioxidant parameters (GSH, GPx, SOD, and CAT)	(26)
22	Quercetin	K562 cells	-	Inhibits total NO, NF- κ B, and COX-2	(52)
23	Puerarin	Male Sprague Dawley rat	LPS	Reduces IL-1 and MMP-9; increases IL-10	(53)
24	Turneron	Male rats	Dimethylhydrazine	Reduces iNOS and COX-2 expression, decreasing NF- κ B transcription activity	(54)
25	Fish oil	Mice	Dextran sulfate sodium (DSS)	Reduces NF- κ B activity and inflammatory score in colonic mucosa	(55)
26	Rhizoma saponins Paridis	Male Sprague Dawley rat	-	Reduces COX-2, IL-1 β , NF- κ B;	(56)

				enhances HO-1, GSH, SOD, and Nrf2 activities	
27	Hydrolyzed collagen and green tea extract	Osteoarthritic human chondrocytes	IL-1 β	Reduces NO, MMP-3, and IL-6	(57)
28	Emu oil	Male Sprague Dawley rat	Carrageenan and CFA	Inhibits paw volume; reduces TNF- α , IL-6, and IL-1 β	(58)
29	Vitamin E	Mice	High calorie	Increases GPx and Nrf-1; reduces lobular inflammatory score and numeric analog scale score	(59)
30	Vitamin B2, carnitine, and N-acetyl-cysteine	16HBE cell	Cigarette smoke extract	Decreases IL-1 β , IL-6, TNF α , and NOS gene expression	(60)
31	Berberine	Male Sprague Dawley rats	High calorie	Decreases SREBP-1, ERK, TNF- α , and JNK expression	(61)
32	Vitamin D3	Adult female Wistar rats	High calorie	Reduces arthritis score and myeloperoxidase activity	(62)
33	Ursodeoxycholic acid	Rat	NAFLD	Increases total antioxidant capacity, GSH, GPx, and SOD; decreases MDA and iNOS	(63)

34	Ursolic acid	Female ICR mice	Tissue plasminogen activator (TPA)	Inhibits IL-1 β , IL-6, IL-19, IL-22, CXCL2, COX-2, and VEGFA	(64)
35	Boswellic acids	Rat	CFA	Reduces paw volume, but does not significantly reduce TNF- α and IL-6	(65)
36	Salidroside	Rat	LPS	Reduces IL-6 and TNF- α	(66)
37	Silymarin	Male Wistar albino rat	Gamma radiation	Decreases IL-18, TNF- α , C-reactive protein, Bax, factor-related apoptosis, and Casp-3 activity	(67)
38	Prednisolone	Rat	Adjuvant-induced arthritis	Reduces TNF- α , IL-1 β , and IL-6 and increases IL-10	(68)
39	Prednisolone	RAW 264.7	LPS	Reduces TNF- α , IL-1 β , and IL-6 and increases IL-10	(68)
40	Thymoquinone	Sprague Dawley rats	Cisplatin	Reduces TNF- α , IL-6, and MCP-1	(69)
41	Flavocoxid	Chondrocytes	LPS	Reduces IL-1 β , NF- κ β , and STAT3 mRNA expression	(70)
42	Tolfenamic acid	Female BALB/c mice	TPA	Reduces COX-2; inhibits IKK and NF- κ β	(71)

43	Luteolin	Male C57BL/6 mice	TNF- α	Reduces TNF- α -induced vascular inflammation	(72)
44	Polyunsaturated fatty acid	RAW 264.7 cells	LPS	Suppresses iNOS, COX-2, 5-lipoxygenase, and cytosolic phospholipase A2	(73)
45	Sulforaphane	RAW 264.7 cells	LPS	Reduces TNF- α , IL-1, NO, and PGE2	(74)
46	Augmentin	Mice	K. pneumoniae	Decreases TNF- α , NO, MPO, and MDA	(75)
47	Saikosaponin A	Male Sprague Dawley rats	CCl4	Decreases interferon- γ , TNF- α , IL-1 β , and IL-6 by inhibiting NF- κ B activation	(76)
48	Essential turmeric oils	Male mice	DSS cholangitis	Increases anti-inflammatory cytokines IL-10 and IL-11	(77)
49	Erythromycin	Rat	Osteomyelitis model	Reduces TNF- α and IL-6, suppresses bone lesions, and decreases histopathological score	(78)
50	Metformin	Male Wistar rat	Gentamicin	Reduces MDA and NO; increases SOD, CAT, GSH, and GPx	(79)
51	Salsalate	Mice	High fat	Reduces IL-1 β and IL-6	(76)

52	Capsaicin	Male Wistar rats	Carrageenan	Reduces paw inflammation and 5-lipoxygenase	(80)
53	Capsaicin	Male Wistar rats	Acetic acid	Inhibits vascular permeability and leukocyte mobilization	(81)
54	Selenium	Male albino Wistar	LPS	Reduces IL-6	(82)
55	Irbesartan	Male albino rats	Streptozotocin	Reduces serum IL-6 and TNF- α	(83)
56	Acetylsalicylic acid	Wistar albino rats	Carrageenan	Decreases paw edema and MDA; increases GSH and SOD	(84)
57	Ginger extract (curcumin-based turmeric extract)	Human PBMCs, RAW 264.7 macrophages	LPS + interferon- γ	Combination strongly inhibited TNF- α , IL-23, and IL-6; reduced iNOS/NO and COX-2/PGE ₂ ; synergistic suppression of NF- κ B, STAT-3, and MAPK (p38, JNK, ERK) vs either extract alone.	(71)
58	Diclofenac sodium	Albino Wistar rats; carrageenan-induced acute paw edema	Carrageenan-induced acute inflammation	Curcumin nanoparticles + diclofenac showed significantly stronger anti-edema and analgesic effects than either drug alone; reduced	(85)

				paw volume and improved pain scores, indicating synergistic or additive interaction.	
59	Chlorogenic acid	Human monocytic THP-1 cells (LPS-stimulated)	LPS-induced inflammation	Chlorogenic acid potentiated curcumin anti-inflammatory activity, reducing IL-6, TNF- α , and NF- κ B-driven gene expression more than curcumin alone; enhanced antioxidant (Nrf-2-linked) and anti-inflammatory effects.	(86)
60	None (different curcumin salts)	Sprague-Dawley rats	Adjuvant-induced arthritis	Various curcumin salts (e.g., curcumin-Cu chelates) showed dose-dependent attenuation of arthritis; effects were comparable to or slightly better than standard curcumin, but not synergistic with a distinct second agent.	(87)
61	Berberine	Male C57BL/6 mice	Acetaminophen-induced liver injury	Curcumin + berberine reduced serum ALT, AST, TNF- α , IL-1 β ,	(88)

				and IL-6 more than either alone; dual inhibition of NF- κ B via PI3K/AKT and PPAR γ pathways, indicating synergistic anti-inflammatory hepatoprotection.	
62	Dimethyl fumarate	Mice	Hepatic ischemia/reperfusion injury	Curcumin + dimethyl fumarate attenuated hepatic injury, lowered serum TNF- α , IL-6, and IL-1 β , and activated Nrf2/HO-1 more than either agent alone, suggesting synergistic anti-inflammatory and antioxidant protection.	(89)
63	Silver nanocomplex (I) (curcumin-Ag)	In vitro Caco-2/HCT-116 co-culture and DSS-induced colitis in mice	DSS-induced colitis	Curcumin-Ag nanocomplex reduced TNF- α , IL-6, iNOS, and MPO more than free curcumin; stronger protection of intestinal barrier and attenuation of oxidative stress, indicating synergistic-like	(90)

				anti-inflammatory action.	
64	EGCG-based nano-antioxidant (curcumin-incorporated)	Mouse models of colitis and nephrotoxicity	DSS-induced colitis / nephrotoxicity	Curcumin-EGCG nano-antioxidants more effectively reduced TNF- α , IL-6, and oxidative markers in colon and kidney than curcumin or EGCG alone, with synergistic anti-inflammatory and antioxidant effects.	(91)
65	Diclofenac (nanoparticle combo)	Rat acute inflammation model	Carrageenan-induced edema and pain	Curcumin-loaded chitosan nanoparticles + diclofenac produced superior anti-edema and analgesic effects vs individual drugs, with reduced inflammation and improved tissue architecture.	(92)
66	Melatonin	EAE mouse model (MS)	Experimental autoimmune encephalomyelitis	Melatonin + curcumin synergistically reduced clinical scores, TNF- α , IL-17, MDA; enhanced SOD, GPx, Nrf2/HO-1 more than monotherapy;	(93)

				combination index <0.8	
67	α -Linolenic acid nanoparticles	HaCaT keratinocytes + imiquimod-induced psoriasis mice	Psoriasis in vitro/in vivo	Curcumin- α -linolenic acid nanoparticles reduced IL-6, IL-17, TNF- α , Ki67 more than curcumin alone; enhanced skin barrier recovery	(94)

Chronic inflammation caused by oxidative stress has a significant impact on the production of TNF- α and nucleus- $\kappa\beta$ (NF- $\kappa\beta$) factor pathways, which increase the inflammatory response. Curcumin inhibits I κ B kinase (IKK) and constitutive NF- $\kappa\beta$. NF- $\kappa\beta$ controls the reduction of proliferation, cell cycle arrest, and apoptosis induction brought on by the blockage of several gene product expression pathways(95).

Enhancing the bioavailability of curcumin

Several studies have been carried out to determine the oral curcumin's bioavailability in experimental rats, which corresponds to about 1% (96). By controlling absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion, medication combinations can have strong or reductive pharmacokinetic effects that can either improve or decrease the therapeutic efficacy of one drug by the other(13). Curcumin has a low pharmacokinetic profile, weak water solubility, and chemical instability. Therefore, regardless of its effectiveness and safety, curcumin's comparatively low bioavailability in humans raises questions about its potential therapeutic function(97). In this review, we discovered that using piperine in combination reduces inflammation more effectively than using it alone. Piperine is a potent bioavailability enhancer that can increase curcumin's

absorption(32). When combined with piperine, curcumin can boost its bioavailability in rats and humans, but it also causes half-time elimination and drastically reduces maximal time and clearance(36). Because piperine lowers the activity of the glucuronidase enzyme, curcumin absorption increases(98). By increasing intestinal perfusion and enterocyte permeability, piperine's additional mechanism improves curcumin's bioavailability(99). Male Wistar rats given 50 mg/kg of curcumin and 2.5 mg/kg of piperine orally for 21 days had lower levels of inflammatory mediator parameters, including NO, TNF- α , and NF- $\kappa\beta$. Piperine inhibits small intestine glucuronidation, which increases curcumin absorption. Additionally, piperine has the ability to slow down curcumin's transit through the digestive tract, prolonging its stay in the intestine and facilitating a higher absorption process(38). Intestinal bacteria, including *Blautia* sp. and *Escherichia coli*, metabolize curcumin. According to (100), these microorganisms are discovered to be active by a NADPH-dependent reductase in a two-step reduction pathway from curcumin to the intermediate product, dihydrocurcumin, and the final product, tetrahydrocurcumin. In the same way, piperine increases the conversion of curcumin into tetrahydrocurcumin through microbial metabolism

in the digestive system. Consequently, the adipose tissue may be reached by this molecule(34). According to (101), the addition of curcumin to emu oil may increase the flux through the mouse skin by 1.84 and 4.25 times, which can lower the expression of proinflammatory mediators IL-1 β , IL-6, and TNF- α (46). This suggests that curcumin is a newly effective treatment for wound healing. Increasing curcumin's bioavailability can be done in conjunction with topical or oral use, according to this review.

Increasing antioxidant

Curcumin's structure contains numerous functional groups, including as carbon-carbon double bonds, β -diketone groups, and phenyl rings with hydroxyl and methoxy substituents. The action of curcumin is significantly influenced by the presence of phenolic OH in the curcumin structure(102). The synergistic impact of the components may boost its effectiveness at low doses to prevent or completely eradicate tissue damage brought on by the start of oxidative stress. By controlling important genes brought on by oxidative stress and preventing the production of cytokines that cause inflammatory pathways, the combination of antioxidants can protect against the development of oxidative stress and inflammation(60). LPS, viruses, proinflammatory cytokines, and oxidative stress can all stimulate NF- $\kappa\beta$, which ultimately controls I κ B α phosphorylation and proteasomal breakdown. In order to produce proinflammatory mediators such cytokines, COX-2, and iNOS, this mechanism will lead to translocation that continues after NF- $\kappa\beta$ binds to the gene promoter region in the nucleus(76).By boosting antioxidant defense through free radical scavenging, resveratrol and curcumin reduce tissue oxidative damage and work in concert to reverse it. By functioning as an antioxidant, resveratrol shields curcumin

molecules from one another(40). Combining curcumin at a dose of 50 mg/kg with quercetin at a dose of 50 mg/kg can boost its anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties in a synergistic way. For four weeks, 100 mg/kg of quercetin and 5 ml/kg of curcumin should be administered. By lowering excessive MDA generation, preserving tissue antioxidant capacity, and enhancing liver enzymatic activity, diazinon-induced rats exhibit a synergistic protective effect (26).The combination of 50 mg/kg of curcumin and 50 mg/kg of berberine has an increased anti-inflammatory impact that may reduce lipid metabolism, oxidative stress, and liver inflammation(61). Additionally, berberine combination treatment has a synergistic effect on lowering oxidative stress and inflammatory responses in rats' hippocampus and cortex(72). The antioxidant capacity is increased by the addition of vitamin E. 1.5 mg/g of vitamin E and 1 mg/g of curcumin raise fatty acid β oxidation, CAT activity, and mitochondrial biogenesis. Hepatic steatosis and lobular inflammation are reduced by the combination(59). Because vitamin B2 stimulates antioxidant genes such heme oxygenase 1 (HO-1), nuclear transcription factor erythroid 2 (Nrf2), and peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor-gamma coactivator-1 alpha, it reduces inflammation(60). Because curcumin is a potent antioxidant that raises SOD, GSH, HO-1, and CAT, it can be added to medications like metformin, acetylsalicylic acid, and Rhizoma Paridis saponins to prevent liver damage(79). Combining curcumin with polyunsaturated fatty acid, docosahexaenoic acid, or eicosapentaenoic acid can increase its anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties in a synergistic manner(73). Curcumin is used in triple therapy regimens for patients with chronic gastritis. These regimens show antioxidant benefits, prevent oxidative damage to DNA cells, and ultimately lower the rate of chronic inflammation(103).

Numerous substances are said to possess antioxidant properties that can directly scavenge reactive oxygen species (ROS), temper the mitochondrial respiratory chain and metal chelating agents, and boost endogenous antioxidant enzymes including glutathione peroxidase, SOD, and CAT(104). Certain mechanisms cause an increase in antioxidant activity, such as the self-protecting mechanism because the combined compound can simultaneously detect multiple antioxidant functions and scavenge certain physiological radical species, inhibit the prooxidant apoenzyme, and reduce and chelate iron ions(105). These elements shield one another from oxidative agents through a range of antioxidant pathways(106). Synergistic antioxidant interactions are made easier by variations in the orientation of the constituents at the water or lipid interface(107).

Inhibiting essential signaling pathways, receptors, and inflammatory mediators

Chemical components interact with inflammatory marker cells and signaling pathways, and these relationships are quite detailed. Reaching the threshold level of pathway activation is crucial for the combination delivery strategy, as the separate components are unable to do so. According to reports, proinflammatory molecules such TNF- α , IL-1 β , IL-6, and NO are inhibited by resveratrol quercetin puerarin, luteolin, and thymoquinone. On RAW 264.7 cells, quercetin and resveratrol(108). decrease inflammatory-inducing enzymes such COX-2 and iNOS, which can also lower NO levels by controlling the NF- κ B pathway. The anti-inflammatory cytokine IL-10 is known to be stimulated by phytochemicals like resveratrol and a class of flavonoids like luteolin and quercetin(109). MDA, TNF α , nitrite levels, COX-1, and COX-2 are all significantly inhibited by flavocoxid(110). By lowering T-cell activation and proliferation, vitamin D and curcumin work

together in response to inflammation and prevent altered lymphocyte activity in rheumatic rats(62). Curcumin exhibits cell-specific interactions, signaling pathways, and inflammatory indicators when combined with these constituents. To provide a synergistic anti-inflammatory action, two or more components can target the same immune cell or distinct cells, controlling the generation of inflammatory markers along the same or alternative routes. Molecular events, such as the activation of immune cells and an increased level of inflammatory enzymes like cytokines, are involved in chronic inflammation that results in carcinogenesis. The pathophysiology of many diseases, including cancer, is initiated by dysregulation of the mammalian target of rapamycin complex 1 (mTORC1). Curcumin and piperine together have a greater ability to control mTORC1 activity than curcumin by itself. In this combination, piperine suppresses COX-2 production and the TNF- α signaling pathway through mTORC1(35). Curcumin and piperine's capacity to inhibit the NF- κ B signaling pathway can cause inflammation; this inhibition prevents TNF- α from being produced and lowers the expression of intercellular protein, adhesion molecule-1, and vascular cell adhesion molecule-1 (VCAM-1)(81).The primary inflammatory mediators, such TNF- α , produce intermediates for a number of chronic inflammatory diseases, autoimmune disorders, and more severe cancers when they are not properly controlled and secreted over time(111). By preventing NF- κ B from translocating into the nucleus, luteolin suppresses TNF- α -induced monocyte adhesion as well as the production of MCP-1 and VCAM-1(112). The combined synergistic impact of curcumin and resveratrol results in a CI value of CI < 1.0 on the prevention of colon cancer growth, which is linked to diminished NF- κ B activity, apoptosis stimulation, and proliferation inhibition(42). It has been demonstrated that curcumin and capsaicin

reduce NF- κ B activation; Animals given carrageenan injections experience the inhibitory impact of inflammation of both components in the enzyme 5-lipoxygenase(80). By preventing NF- κ B from being activated, a combination of curcuminoid extract, hydrolyzed collagen, and green tea extract can lower inflammation as well as the production of inflammatory and catabolic mediators by chondrocytes(57). Because resveratrol can hold onto phosphorylated I κ B α and prevent activated NF- κ B from moving to the nucleus, both curcumin and resveratrol have the ability to suppress the NF- κ B signal transduction pathway. Curcumin also has the effect of reducing the translocation of activated NF- κ B to the nucleus(41). The primary signaling proteins in response to inflammation, cytokines, are involved in the inflammatory process. Growth factor β and interferon γ are altered by the proinflammatory cytokines IL-1, IL-6, IL-15, IL-17, IL-23, and TNF- α and the anti-inflammatory cytokines IL-4, IL-10, and IL-13(113). One significant class of cytokines that is crucial for immunological regulation is interleukins. This modulation includes IL-1, which controls the transformation of phagocytes that infiltrate during cancer or inflammation, causing the production of inflammatory molecules like chemokines, integrins, and MMP as well as free radicals like ROS and reactive nitrogen species(114). At a dose of 1 grams per kilogram and piperine at a dose of 50 milligrams per kilogram can both considerably lower IL-1 β and reduce the weight of mice caused by excessive fat(37). If unchecked production results in a variety of inflammatory disorders, the presence of IL-6 is crucial in acute inflammation(115). Curcumin and ursolic acid together have a big impact. on preventing I κ B α and NF- κ B from being phosphorylated. The NF- κ B signaling pathway is inhibited by lower COX-2 protein levels and lower production of inflammatory marker genes such IL-1 β , IL-6, and

CXCL2(64). In LPS-induced Sprague Dawley rats, puerarin with curcumin boosts anti-inflammatory cytokines like IL-10 and lowers proinflammatory cytokines like IL-1 β and MMP-9, making it more effective and nontoxic(53). Mice with LPS exhibit altered behavior and elevated cytokine levels, whereas mice given 5 mg/kg salidroside and 20 mg/kg curcumin exhibit antidepressant-like effects similar to those of fluoxetine, as well as possible synergistic reduction of TNF- α and IL-6 and anti-stress effects(66).By blocking the activity of the inhibitory I- κ B kinase, the anti-inflammatory combination regulates several pathways, inhibits the MAPK pathway, and stimulates NF- κ B generated by cytokines and proinflammatory gene expression. Additionally, it prevents the production of prostaglandins by inhibiting iNOS expression, arachidonic acid pathways, and the proinflammatory cytokine synthesis pathway. This suppresses immune cell migration and proliferation, which in turn prevents inflammation.

CONCLUSION

Enhanced antioxidants, enhanced curcumin bioavailability, modulation of many pathways, and inflammatory markers all contribute to the curcumin combination's anti-inflammatory action. In order to reduce the consequences of oxidative stress, the combination with certain components can directly scavenge enhanced ROS and boost antioxidants. Further reduction of the NF- κ B signaling pathway is directly regulated by the decreased ROS. Proinflammatory indicators' transcription and translation processes are deregulated by attenuated NF- κ B, while antiinflammatory molecules are elevated. Combining curcumin with piperine can boost its bioavailability. This review offers suggestions for further investigation into the use of chemicals in combination to lower inflammation. The present

analysis has given an outline of how inflammation's molecular mechanisms occur, their pharmaceutical remedies, and the manner in which the present review has offered An outline of how inflammation's molecular mechanisms occur, their pharmacological therapies, and the potential interactions between curcumin molecules in their pharmacological effects while preventing negative side effects. The evolution of Drug combination techniques is crucial for more effective treatment of a range of inflammatory diseases, both acute and chronic. In this review, we gathered and examined curcumin research data. combination and determined that there are multiple elements to be used in addition with curcumin to provide anti-inflammatory activity, and clinical trials have included such experiments.

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